

USE OF LOW-CALORIE SWEETENERS IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES: BENEFITS, RISKS AND SCIENTIFIC EVIDENCE

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Abstract. Today, one in eleven adults is diagnosed with diabetes, with approximately 90% of cases being type 2 diabetes (T2D). In recent years, the incidence and mortality rates associated with type 2 diabetes have been steadily increasing. Moreover, 280 million people have been diagnosed with impaired carbohydrate metabolism, particularly impaired glucose tolerance. This number does not include individuals who are unaware of their condition, which is estimated to be 3–4 times higher than the number of officially diagnosed cases. Type 2 diabetes is characterized by impaired carbohydrate metabolism and reduced tissue sensitivity to insulin, which necessitates blood glucose control, including limiting sugar intake. Chronic hyperglycemia leads to well-known complications, such as microvascular and macrovascular damage, as well as injury to peripheral and autonomic nerves. Maintaining normal blood glucose levels in type 2 diabetes can be achieved through well-structured nutrition. Effective disease management requires a clear understanding of which foods are contraindicated, which should be limited, and which can be consumed freely. Keeping a food diary helps monitor the diet and improve dietary control, contributing to the normalization of disturbed fat and carbohydrate metabolism. The use of sweeteners has become an important component of dietary therapy for this condition.

The article analyzes various types of sweeteners differing in their origin (natural and synthetic), chemical structure, sweetness compared to sugar, as well as metabolic effects and their influence on blood glucose levels. Natural sweeteners such as stevia, erythritol, and xylitol—derived from natural sources and characterized by low or zero glycemic index—are reviewed. Synthetic sweeteners (e.g., aspartame, sucralose, acesulfame K), which have a high degree of sweetness and minimal caloric value, are also discussed. The article explores the advantages and potential risks of using different sweeteners in type 2 diabetes, including their effects on appetite, gut microbiota, body weight, and overall health. Special attention is given to their benefits, such as low caloric content and no effect on blood glucose levels, as well as to possible risks associated with long-term use. The need for an individualized approach to selecting sweeteners is emphasized, taking into account comorbidities, patient tolerance, and lifestyle factors.

The aim of this article is to review the scientific literature in order to analyze and evaluate the effects of non-caloric sweeteners on glycemic control parameters in patients with type 2 diabetes.

Keywords: sugar substitutes, low-calorie sweeteners, sugar replacements.

Introduction. Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is one of the most significant public health challenges today. As of 2017, the global prevalence of this disease among the adult population was 6.3%, and according to forecasts, it may reach 7.4% by 2040 [2]. Diabetic complications increase mortality rates and healthcare costs. Treatment strategies aimed at preventing diabetes-related complications focus on controlling blood glucose levels, blood pressure, and lipid profiles.

Patients often use sugar substitutes to enhance the taste of their foods and beverages while avoiding excessive calorie and carbohydrate intake [8].

Studies have shown that adherence to a Mediterranean or plant-based diet helps reduce symptoms of T2DM, slows its progression and complications, and effectively lowers glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) levels, comparable to pharmacological therapy. Weight loss in obese patients can also be achieved through consistent adherence to the principles of healthy eating [13].

According to World Health Organization (WHO) recommendations regarding macronutrient intake, an adult's daily diet should consist of 55–75% carbohydrates, 10–15% proteins, and 15–30% fats. For a 2000 kcal/day diet, this roughly corresponds to about 165 g of fats, 40 g of carbohydrates, and 75 g of proteins [11]. In type 2 diabetes, it is essential to control both the amount and quality of carbohydrates, as they directly affect postprandial glucose levels. Different types of carbohydrates affect glycemia differently: some cause a gradual rise and fall in blood sugar, while others lead to rapid spikes and drops [14]. Free sugars should make up no more than 5% of total daily energy intake [7].

Non-caloric sweeteners are used in very small amounts to provide sweetness, as they are at least 100 times sweeter than regular sugar. There is a hypothesis that substituting caloric sweeteners with non-caloric ones may lead people to consume more food to compensate for the "saved" calories [8]. Artificial sweeteners are found in thousands of food and beverage brands worldwide, yet their use remains controversial. The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the World Health Organization, and other health agencies are currently reviewing the issue [7].

Currently, low-calorie sweeteners are recommended for adults with diabetes and obesity who consume excessive amounts of easily digestible carbohydrates. Natural sugar substitutes are considered safe when used within acceptable daily intake levels; however, their use may be limited due to lower sweetness, aftertaste, or undesirable texture. Combining different sweeteners can help improve taste profiles. Some artificial sweeteners, such as sucralose and acesulfame potassium, may adversely affect gut microbiota, metabolism, and eating behavior. Long-term studies are needed to more accurately assess the safety and efficacy of various sweeteners [1].

A study conducted in the United States found that out of 85,000 food items purchased over the past decade, approximately 75% contained some form of sweetener. These substances were found in cakes, baked goods, muesli, sports bars, ready-to-eat cereals, sweet snacks, and sugar-sweetened beverages [12]. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has approved six non-caloric sweeteners as food additives: aspartame, acesulfame potassium, saccharin, sucralose, neotame, and advantame. Monk fruit extract (*Siraitia grosvenorii* Swingle) and steviol glycosides (*Stevia rebaudiana*) are also permitted for use in food products under specific conditions. In the European Union (EU), approved substances include steviol glycosides, cyclamate, thaumatin, neohesperidin dihydrochalcone, and the aspartame-acesulfame salt. According to available data, sweeteners are considered safe when consumed within acceptable daily intake limits. This recommendation has been assigned a Grade A level of evidence, indicating high-quality supporting data [1].

Artificial Sweeteners and Their Impact on Metabolism

Artificial sweeteners, which reproduce a sweet taste without the use of sugar and thereby reduce the caloric intake from free sugars, have been widely appreciated by consumers as an alternative to added sugar [7]. The American Heart Association (AHA) and the American Diabetes Association (ADA) cautiously recommend the use of artificial sweeteners as a sugar substitute in

managing obesity, metabolic syndrome, and diabetes—conditions that are risk factors for cardiovascular disease [12].

Non-caloric sweeteners activate sweet taste receptors (T1R2 + T1R3) not only in the mouth but also in other organs, including the gastrointestinal tract, adipose tissue, and the pancreas, influencing metabolism via neural and hormonal pathways. Activation of sweet taste receptors in the small intestine enhances glucose absorption and stimulates the release of incretins, including GLP-1, while also regulating hormones responsible for hunger and satiety [9]. Artificial sweeteners (AS) have become a potential tool in diabetes management [3]. Millions of people consume artificial sweeteners daily, which are present in thousands of different products [2].

Today, artificial sweeteners are widely used in food and beverages as sugar substitutes and are sometimes recommended for weight control and for individuals with type 2 diabetes (T2DM). They are commonly found in a variety of foods and drinks labeled as “diet” or “sugar-free.” Since many product labels do not indicate the quantity of artificial sweeteners, it is difficult to assess the actual intake by individuals [4]. It is known that artificial sweeteners help with weight control, an important factor in reducing diabetes risk. Furthermore, AS do not affect immediate blood glucose levels, allowing better glucose control in diabetic individuals. However, artificial sweeteners may influence gut microbiota, potentially altering its composition and affecting metabolic health. This interaction has raised concerns about insulin sensitivity and the potential risk of insulin resistance [3].

Studied Sweeteners. The increasing use of non-caloric sweeteners in food production has made studying their potential metabolic effects increasingly important [1]. Research suggests that non-caloric sweeteners may help reduce postprandial hyperglycemia in patients with type 2 diabetes and in obese individuals as part of a comprehensive weight loss program. Other studies, however, show that some non-caloric sweeteners negatively affect carbohydrate metabolism [1].

In one randomized, controlled, cross-over study, the effects of saccharin on glucose and insulin levels were assessed in 17 patients with type 2 diabetes. At no stage after saccharin intake were there statistically significant changes in plasma glucose, insulin, or glucagon levels [8].

Currently, saccharin, aspartame, and cyclamate are the most commonly used sugar substitutes in diet beverages and food products [6]. Aspartame has been the most extensively studied non-caloric sweetener in terms of its effect on glycemic control. In a study by Okuno et al., diabetic participants (n = 9) consumed a jelly dessert containing 125 mg of aspartame daily for two weeks. No statistically significant changes were observed in glucose tolerance test results (50 g), postprandial glycemia, total cholesterol, HDL cholesterol, or triglyceride levels. The most common side effects were mild gastrointestinal symptoms [8].

A cross-sectional study using a combination of saccharin and cyclamate was conducted at the Diabetes Center of Azadi General Teaching Hospital in Duhok, Kurdistan Region, Iraq. Among 181 diabetic patients, 88 consumed sweeteners (DS group), and the remaining 93 did not (D group). Additionally, 82 healthy individuals were divided into two groups: 14 consumed sweeteners (HS), and 68 did not (H). According to the study, the saccharin-cyclamate mixture increased HbA1c, triglycerides, LDL, and total cholesterol/HDL ratio, while HDL levels decreased in both healthy individuals and diabetic patients [6].

In both healthy individuals and patients with diabetes, long-term consumption of saccharin-cyclamate mixtures induces oxidative stress. The intake of these sweeteners impairs glycemic control, increases the risk of atherosclerosis, and adversely affects liver and kidney function. Animal studies convincingly show that artificial sweeteners contribute to weight gain due to the

accumulation of sugar in tissues. Although blood sugar levels do not rise upon consumption of artificial sweeteners, the sweet taste triggers an insulin response, potentially leading to hypoglycemia and increased food intake. In experiments, rats given artificial sweeteners consumed more calories over time, resulting in obesity and weight gain. This confuses the body's regulatory mechanisms, leading to loss of appetite control and overeating [6].

In a randomized cross-over study, S. Tey and colleagues investigated the effects of beverages sweetened with sucrose and non-caloric sweeteners (monk fruit, aspartame, stevia) on insulin response, glucose fluctuations, and changes in daily energy intake. This study was conducted over one day with healthy male volunteers with a normal BMI (18.5–25.0 kg/m²). During the first hour, the sucrose group showed a rapid increase in postprandial glycemia; in the non-caloric sweetener (NCS) groups, similar changes occurred after meals composed of slowly digestible carbohydrates. The sucrose, aspartame, stevia, and monk fruit subgroups all exhibited similar total AUCs (areas under the curve) for glucose and insulin. Other studies have shown that in healthy individuals, NCS consumption does not trigger the release of insulin, gastric inhibitory peptide (GIP), or glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) [1].

Sucralose is a non-caloric sweetener derived from sucrose, approved for use in food and beverages worldwide. It is approximately 600 times sweeter than sugar, so even minimal amounts provide sufficient sweetness. Sucralose does not raise blood glucose levels, making it suitable for individuals with diabetes seeking to reduce calorie and carbohydrate intake [10]. In a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled study, the effects of sucralose at a dose of 667 mg/day (n = 67) versus placebo (n = 69) were evaluated for glycemic control in patients with type 2 diabetes. Participants measured their capillary blood glucose levels at least three times per day. No significant differences in HbA1c levels were observed between the groups, and no adverse effects were reported [8].

Steviol glycosides, natural high-intensity sweeteners, are not hydrolyzed by gastrointestinal enzymes and remain unchanged in the colon. There, gut bacteria of the *Bacteroides* genus break them down into steviol, which is absorbed in the liver and subsequently excreted from the body. Stevia extract has been shown to promote the growth of *Bifidobacteria* and *Lactobacilli* in vitro and to suppress *E. coli* growth in mice [1].

Stevia contains various steviol glycosides, the most common and sweetest of which are stevioside and rebaudioside A. To evaluate their impact on blood glucose levels, two randomized controlled trials involving 152 patients with type 1 and type 2 diabetes were conducted [8].

In a parallel trial that included 16 patients with type 1 diabetes (T1DM), 30 patients with type 2 diabetes (T2DM), and 30 healthy volunteers, Barriocanal and colleagues examined the effects of steviol glycosides on blood glucose and blood pressure. Over a period of three months, participants received 250 mg of steviol glycosides in capsules or placebo three times a day. There were no statistically significant changes observed in systolic or diastolic blood pressure, fasting glucose, or HbA1c in the healthy and T2DM groups. However, in the T1DM group, significant differences were noted in systolic blood pressure and fasting glucose compared to placebo [8,15].

In a clinical trial involving 34 patients with T2DM, the effects of the natural sweetener stevia were compared to sucralose, an artificial sweetener. Fifteen participants consumed one cup of 2% sweet tea with stevia extract at three meals, while nineteen others took a daily sucralose tablet for eight weeks. Glycemic response, lipid profile, height, weight, BMI, and dietary intake were measured. No significant differences were found in glycemic response, lipid profile, insulin, HbA1c, or blood lipids between the two groups [5].

Sensory analyses have been conducted to assess how different concentrations of stevia affect various food products, including cheeses of varying fat content and baked goods. Results showed that the food matrix, particularly fat and protein content, influenced sweetness perception and the metallic aftertaste characteristic of stevia. Products with low fat content exhibited a more pronounced metallic aftertaste at the same stevia concentration, while high-fat products retained better taste and experienced minimal sensory changes. Overall, stevia-sweetened products matched sugar-containing counterparts in sensory quality and offered lower calorie content with potentially better health profiles [12,15].

Polyols and Their Effect on the Gut Microbiota. Polyols (sorbitol, mannitol, xylitol, erythritol, maltitol, lactitol, isomalt) occur naturally in fruits, vegetables, and mushrooms, and are widely used in food production. Some—like sorbitol, mannitol, xylitol, and erythritol—can be produced by microbes via natural or genetically engineered pathways. As natural low-calorie sweeteners, they are substantially metabolized by gut microbiota, exerting prebiotic effects. They influence gut microbial composition, stimulate bacterial metabolites, and elicit various biological effects that warrant further clinical research. Their use can be limited in individuals with functional gastrointestinal disorders, such as irritable bowel syndrome (IBS), due to symptom exacerbation [1].

Conclusion. The use of non-caloric sweeteners in type 2 diabetes may serve as an effective strategy for glycemic control and reducing total sugar intake. These sweeteners help maintain flavor in foods and beverages without risking glycemic spikes. They also aid in lowering the caloric content of the diet, which is crucial for weight management—a key component in diabetes care.

However, selection and dosing must be personalized and supervised by a healthcare professional, as prolonged or excessive intake may have potential side effects. Stevia, erythritol, and sucralose are considered the safest and most commonly recommended sweeteners.

Moderate and rational use of sweeteners can benefit comprehensive type 2 diabetes therapy by enhancing patients' quality of life and stabilizing glycemic control. Natural non-caloric sweeteners—particularly polyols like erythritol and xylitol—have shown positive effects on carbohydrate metabolism and body weight, making them promising in the context of obesity and diabetes. They also enhance insulin secretion and gut hormone responses, supporting metabolic syndrome treatment. However, most studies are short-term, and their findings require confirmation in long-term trials.

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